

GUN VIOLENCE IN AMERICA: AN EVALUATION AND ANALYSIS OF FEDERAL GUN

LAWS

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Preface

The Second Amendment of the United States Constitution states, "A well regulated Militia, being necessary to the security of a free State, the right of the people to keep and bear Arms, shall not be infringed."¹ Regardless of what the proper interpretation of the Second Amendment was, it has generally granted Americans access to buy, possess, and use guns in the United States and thus, has served as a significant part of our freedom and cultural DNA, especially for all gun owners.² As a result, guns are deeply embedded in American culture. According to a national survey from the National Institute of Justice, approximately 44 million people own almost 200 million firearms.³ Recently, as of 2009, it has been estimated that about 310 million firearms are available to civilians.⁴ These statistics highlight how highly guns are valued in America, verifying the popularity and support of gun possession in American culture.

However, a consequence of this culture has been high levels of gun violence. For several decades, this violence has been a prominent issue in the United States. According to various sources, tens of thousands of Americans die every year from gun-related injuries, predominantly made up of suicides and murders. Specifically, as of 2020, in the United States, "45,222 people died from gun-related injuries."⁵ Of all murders and suicides in 2020, about 80% of murders involved a firearm, and about 53% of suicides involved a gun.⁶ When looking at the data on

¹ U.S. Const. amend. II.

² Parker, et al., "America's Complex Relationship with Guns." Pew Research Center's Social & Demographic Trends Project. Pew Research Center, February 3, 2022. <https://www.pewresearch.org/social-trends/2017/06/22/americas-complex-relationship-with-guns/>.

³ William J. Krouse, *Gun Control Legislation*, CRS Report No. RL32842 (Washington, DC: Congressional Research Service, 2012), 8, <https://sgp.fas.org/crs/misc/RL32842.pdf>.

⁴ Ibid

⁵ John Gramlich, "What the data says about gun deaths in the U.S." Pew Research Center, February 3, 2022. <https://www.pewresearch.org/fact-tank/2022/02/03/what-the-data-says-about-gun-deaths-in-the-u-s/>.

⁶ Ibid.

firearm deaths from decades ago, gun deaths rates were even higher in the past, particularly in the 70s when it was at their peak high. In comparison, while there were 6.2 murders and 7.0 suicides per 100,000 people from guns in 2020, the rate of gun murders in 1974 was 7.2 and 7.7 for gun suicides in 1977.⁷

These statistics stemming from firearm deaths reveal the ongoing issue of gun violence in America.

In response to this violence, the federal and state governments have attempted to enact firearms regulations that aimed to reduce gun violence in America. Specifically, since 1813 when "Kentucky passed legislation prohibiting the carrying of concealed weapons," firearms have been regulated.⁸ As a result, tens of thousands of federal, state, and local laws regulate firearms.⁹ As mentioned above, however, it's clear that gun violence rates remain high despite these regulations. Even though laws regulating firearms are meant to restrain the number of homicides, suicides, and injuries from illegal gun use, tens of thousands of people are still killed and injured by guns annually. So, what effect have gun laws been in limiting unlawful gun use in the United States?

To answer the question, this paper will explore the relationship between firearm laws and gun violence in the United States. In particular, as the entire paper looks at federal firearms laws, the majority of this paper concentrates on examining one primary component of federal firearms legislation, which specifically looks at federal restrictions on the transfer and possession of firearms. So, to summarize the context of this paper, there are five sections that make up this paper. The first section will include a brief overview of the federal statutory framework on

⁷ Ibid.

⁸ "Gun Control - Take That! and That! the Gun Control Debate Continues, Further Readings." Firearms, Act, Federal, and Court - JRank Articles. <https://law.jrank.org/pages/7258/Gun-Control.html>.

⁹ Ibid.

firearms. The second section will then further explore federal firearms laws in more depth and provide an overview of some of their significant regulations on firearms, which will include federal provisions on the possession and transfer of firearms. Section three includes an analysis of how successfully these regulations have limited gun violence in the United States, relying on pre-existing research sources. According to my findings, there are certain reasons that make these regulations not as effective as they should be. To be specific, these reasons come about from the gaps in federal law on firearm transfers. From this analysis, modifications to these regulations are emphasized and considered in section four. Finally, section five describes selected topical areas relating to the regulations above where Congress has currently considered legislation to amend these existing federal regulations on firearms.

I. Federal Statutory Framework on Firearms

For almost a century, federal law has regulated firearms, using the Commerce Clause and the Taxing and Spending Clause as its constitutional basis for doing so. However, federal firearms regulations based on the exercise of the commerce and taxing powers must be consistent with those powers, resulting in a limited and basic federal statutory framework of firearms.¹⁰ As a result, “Federal law establishes a regulatory framework for the lawful manufacture, sale, and possession of firearms at the national level.”¹¹ It’s understood that federal firearms laws generally serve as the minimum regulations on guns, which every State must comply with. With this in mind, although states cannot make any laws that conflict with federal law, states can supplement with additional firearm restrictions that further regulate guns.

¹⁰ Michal A. Foster, *Federal Firearms Laws: Overview and Selected Legal Issues for the 116th Congress*, CRS Report No. R45629 (Washington, DC: Congressional Research Service, 2019), at front page, <https://crsreports.congress.gov/product/pdf/R/R45629>

¹¹ *Ibid.*

In 1919, Congress established an excise tax on imported firearms and ammunition. In 1934, the National Firearms Act was enacted by Congress, which “established a stringent taxation and registration scheme for specified weapons associated with the Prohibition-fueled gang violence of the time.”¹² Four years later, in 1938, the Federal Firearms Act was enacted by Congress, which “created a licensing scheme for the manufacture, importation, and sale of firearms and established limited categories of persons who could not possess firearms.”¹³ A few decades later, though, the Gun Control Act of 1968 was passed, which superseded and replaced the FFA, “expanding the FFA’s licensing scheme and categories of prohibited persons.”¹⁴ Since then, the GCA has served as the most fundamental firearm statute enacted by the federal government. As a result, over the years since, the GCA has been amended by various additional firearm regulations, such as the Firearm Owners’ Protection Act of 1986 (FOPA), the Brady Handgun Violence Protection Act of 1993, the Gun-Free School Zones Act, and the Youth Handgun Safety Act of 1994.

In particular, FOPA “carved out exceptions to the felony firearm prohibition for certain crimes, repealed certain regulations pertaining to ammunition, expressly prohibited the creation of a national gun registry, added additional categories of persons who are barred from possessing firearms, prohibited the private possession of machineguns manufactured on or after the date of FOPA’s enactment, and further expanded the available criminal penalties for violations.”¹⁵ The Brady Act amended the GCA’s transfer requirements with a more comprehensive system that relies on a background check system to indicate whether or not a transferee is “ineligible to

¹² Ibid, 1-2.

¹³ Ibid, 2 (citing Pub. L. No. 75-785, 52 Stat. 1250 (1938)).

¹⁴ Ibid.

¹⁵ Ibid, (citing Pub. L. No. 99-308, 100 Stat. 449 (1986)).

receive a firearm."¹⁶ The Gun-Free School Zones Act amended the GCA's prohibitions on firearm possession by banning firearms in "statutorily defined school zones."¹⁷ The Youth Handgun Safety Act amended the GCA by banning the "possession of handguns by persons under the age of 18, and prohibiting "adults from transferring handguns to juveniles."¹⁸

Additionally, Congress passed the Violent Crime Control and Law Enforcement Act of 1994, which enacted various "substantive criminal" provisions and "immigration initiatives."¹⁹ Of these provisions, the assault weapons ban was formed, which imposed a 10-year ban on "the manufacture of 19 military-style assault weapons, assault weapons with specific combat features, "copy-cat" models, and certain high-capacity ammunition magazines of more than ten rounds."²⁰ In recent years, in 2005, the Protection of Lawful Commerce in Arms Act was enacted by Congress, which granted certain civil immunities to lawful firearm owners, manufacturers, importers, and dealers.²¹

II. Prohibiting Certain Transfers and Possession of Firearms

As all federal firearms laws are part of the federal government's comprehensive approach to addressing the enduring problem of gun violence in the United States, which makes them all significant and noteworthy, I will however concentrate on further examining a certain set of federal firearms regulations that have been known to be the most fundamental. Thus, this paper

¹⁶ Ibid, 18.

¹⁷ Ibid, 2.

¹⁸ Department of Justice, Gun Violence Reduction: National Integrated Firearms Violence Reduction Strategy, (Washington, DC: Department of Justice), <https://www.justice.gov/archive/opd/AppendixC.htm#Text%201>.

¹⁹ Department of Justice, *Violent Crime Control and Law Enforcement Act of 1994*, NCJ FS000067, (Washington, DC: Department of Justice 1994), <https://www.ncjrs.gov/txtfiles/billfs.txt>.

²⁰ Ibid.

²¹ Foster, *Federal Firearms Laws: Overview and Selected Legal Issues for the 116th Congress*, 1.

will again and more deeply examine the GCA and the Brady Act, looking at a particular set of their most significant and primary firearms regulations.

For several decades, one primary objective the federal government has concentrated on is establishing ways to keep guns out of the hands of criminals and others who have exhibited significant risk factors that could potentially lead to future violence or self-harm.²² With this in mind, it's been found that individuals with certain characteristics and past histories that elevate their risk of committing violence and unlawful acts are likely to use a firearm for the wrong purposes and thus cause unnecessary harm and violence.²³ Various sources, including government research reports as well as governmental and general articles, indicate this connection. So, as previously mentioned, to protect public health and safety from unlawful firearm use and still give way for firearms to be accessible in the United States, the federal government has found it necessary to establish regulations that prohibit certain persons from acquiring and possessing firearms.²⁴ As a result, in 1968, the federal government passed the Gun Control Act, which created the first comprehensive federal framework primarily intended to prevent certain high-risk and dangerous persons from possessing firearms. This objective is even indicated in the first part of the GCA's stated goals, which provides to "keep firearms out of the hands of those not legally entitled to possess them because of age, criminal background or incompetency, and to assist law enforcement authorities in the states and their subdivisions in combating the increasing prevalence of crime in the United States."²⁵

²² Department of Justice, *Gun Violence Reduction: National Integrated Firearms Violence Reduction Strategy*, appendix c.

²³ Ibid.

²⁴ Foster, *Federal Firearms Laws: Overview and Selected Legal Issues for the 116th Congress*, 1-46.

²⁵ Department of Justice, *Gun Violence Reduction: National Integrated Firearms Violence Reduction Strategy*, appendix c.

Thus, ever since the enactment of the GCA, federal law requires “individuals engaged in the business of dealing firearms to obtain a federal license,” prohibits the “transfer and possession of firearms to certain persons,” restricts the “interstate transportation of firearms,” and regulates the “importation of certain firearms not suitable for sporting purposes.”²⁶ Out of these four key provisions of the GCA, its licensing requirements as well as its prohibitions on certain transfers and possession of firearms served for more than two decades as the main provisions to complete this primary goal--constraining high-risk individuals from acquiring and using firearms until the Brady Act amended them. With this in mind, in 1993, the federal government amended and improved the GCA’s transfer restrictions with the enactment of the Brady Act, which required background checks.²⁷ Since then, the GCA, as amended by Brady, has been the leading federal legal measure that addresses the problem of dangerous persons occupying guns.

A. Requiring Federal Licenses for Transferring Firearms

Since the passage of the GCA, federal law has applied gun licensing requirements and prohibitions on firearm access that have been supplemented regularly. Specifically, federal law requires importers, manufacturers, and dealers engaged in the business of firearms to obtain a federal firearms license to deal with firearms lawfully.²⁸ The determinants for being "engaged in the business" depend on "certain relevant factors that include (1) the quantity and frequency of firearms sales; (2) sale location; (3) how the sales occurred; (4) the defendant's behavior before, during, and after the sales; (5) the type of firearms sold and prices charged; and (6) the

²⁶ Ibid.

²⁷ House of Representatives (H.R.) 1025 - 103rd Congress (1993-1994): Brady Handgun Violence Prevention Act <https://www.congress.gov/bill/103rd-congress/house-bill/1025>.

²⁸ Foster, *Federal Firearms Laws: Overview and Selected Legal Issues for the 116th Congress*, 6-7.

defendant's intent at the time of the sales.”²⁹ In other words, an individual "engaged in the business of dealing in firearms" is one who devotes time and devotion to firearm transactions and also seeks to make a profit.³⁰

Thus, persons who find themselves engaged in the firearm business must meet specific requirements to become federal firearm licensees (FFLs). These requirements include "being at least 21 years of age, maintaining a premises from which to conduct business that meets safety standards, and certifying compliance with applicable state and local laws.”³¹ Suppose a person meets these requirements and receives their federal firearm license. In that case, they are also required to comply with various requirements that mandate them to recordkeeping, identifying "imported or manufactured firearms by means of a serial number," and complying with transfer restrictions, such as background check requirements.³²

B. Prohibitions on Certain Persons from Possessing Firearms

As for the regulations of the GCA regarding "prohibited persons," as amended, the GCA prohibits the possession of a firearm to any of the following:³³

1. “Persons who are convicted of a crime punishable by imprisonment for a term exceeding one year, even if the person received a shorter sentence.
2. Persons who are fugitives from justice.
3. Persons who are unlawful users of and/or addicted to any controlled substance.
4. Persons who are adjudicated mental defective or involuntarily committed to a mental institution.
5. Persons who are aliens illegally/unlawfully in the United States and nonimmigrant aliens (with certain limited exceptions).

²⁹ Ibid.

³⁰ Department of Justice, *Do I Need a License to Buy and Sell Firearms?* (Washington, DC: Department of Justice, 2016), 4, <https://www.atf.gov/file/100871/download>.

³¹ Foster, *Federal Firearms Laws: Overview and Selected Legal Issues for the 116th Congress*, 7.

³² Ibid.

³³ Department of Justice, National Instant Criminal Background Check System (NICS) Federal Firearms Licensee Manual. FBI. FBI, June 4, 2016. <https://www.fbi.gov/file-repository/nics-firearms-licensee-manual-111811.pdf/view>.

6. Persons who have been dishonorably discharged from the United States Armed Forces.
7. Persons who have renounced their United States citizenship.
8. Persons who are the subject of certain protection orders.
9. Persons who have been convicted of a misdemeanor crime of domestic violence.
10. Persons who are under indictment (information) for a crime punishable by imprisonment for a term exceeding one year.”

C. Restricting the Transfer of Firearms to Prohibited Persons

While the GCA makes it unlawful for prohibited persons to possess firearms, it also makes it unlawful for these prohibited persons to receive firearms. Specifically, federal law makes it a “felony for an FFL or any person to transfer a firearm knowing, or having reasonable cause to believe, that the transferee is prohibited from receiving the firearm.”³⁴ To help FFLs know if a purchaser falls into one of these prohibiting groups is by also requiring unlicensed gun purchasers to fill out form 4473 prior to buying a firearm from an FFL, answering whether or not they have had a felony conviction or any other disqualifying condition.³⁵

Since this check system relied on prospective purchasers to truthfully admit to any disqualifying characteristics if they had any, this led FFLs not to know whether customers were “lying about their background in order to get a gun.”³⁶ So, prior to being amended with a more improved transfer system by the Brady Act in 1993, if a person who was aware that they fell into one of these prohibited categories, such as a felon or drug addict, they could still purchase a firearm from an FFL as long as they lied about themselves when completing form 4473.

³⁴ Department of Justice, *Gun Violence Reduction: National Integrated Firearms Violence Reduction Strategy*, appendix c.

³⁵ Cook, Philip J and Jens Ludwig. 2013 ‘The Limited Impact of the Brady Act - Introduction of the Brady Act.’ *Reducing Gun Violence in America: Informing Policy with Evidence and Analysis*; Part I, Chapter 2, p. 22. Baltimore, MD: Johns Hopkins University Press. 25 January

³⁶ Department of Justice, *Gun Violence Reduction: National Integrated Firearms Violence Reduction Strategy*, appendix c.

To ensure prohibited individuals are barred from buying guns, the federal government passed the Brady Act in 1993, which replaced this unworking requirement with a more comprehensive and improved transfer check scheme. It was enacted in 1993 to provide a more suitable method for "blocking transfers of firearms to prohibited persons."³⁷ The first version of the Brady Act known as the "interim Brady provisions," which was in effect from February 28, 1994 to November 30, 1998, required "a Federal Firearms Licensee (FFL) to request a background check on a handgun applicant from the Chief Law Enforcement Officer (CLEO) of the jurisdiction where the licensee operated" prior to selling or transferring any handgun.³⁸ If there was no notice of denial within five days by the CLEO, the handgun could be legally transferred.³⁹ However, the Supreme Court's ruling in 1997⁴⁰ found these provisions unconstitutional and thus, nullified the interim Brady provisions, grounding their ruling on the "usurpation of state executive prerogatives."⁴¹

Thereby, in November of 1998, a new version of the Brady Act was passed, known as "permanent Brady," which "provides for the establishment of a national instant criminal background check system (NICS) that federal firearm licensees must contact before transferring any firearm to unlicensed individuals."⁴² Specifically, the Brady Act's permanent provisions required for the establishment of the National Instant Background Check System (NICS) by the

³⁷ Ronald J. Frandsen, "Enforcement of the Brady Act, 2008: Federal and State Investigations and Prosecutions of Firearm Applicants Denied by a NICS Check in 2008" (hereinafter "Enforcement of the Brady Act"), Department of Justice, June 2010, Document No: 231052, <https://www.ojp.gov/pdffiles1/bjs/231052.pdf>.

³⁸ *Ibid*, 3.

³⁹ *Ibid*.

⁴⁰ *Printz v. United States*, 521 U.S. 898, 935 (1997).

⁴¹ Foster, *Federal Firearms Laws: Overview and Selected Legal Issues for the 116th Congress*, 18.

⁴² Department of the Treasury, *Open Letter to All Alabama Federal Firearms Licensees*, (Washington, DC: Department of the Treasury, 1998), <https://www.atf.gov/firearms/docs/open-letter/alabama-oct1998-open-letter-permanent-provisions-brady-law/download>

U.S. Attorney General that FFLs contact prior to transferring a firearm to an unlicensed individual.⁴³ So when the NICS came about in 1998, it was developed by the Federal Bureau of Investigation (FBI) “in cooperation with the Bureau of Alcohol, Tobacco, Firearms and Explosives (BATF), U.S. Department of Justice, and State and local law enforcement agencies.”⁴⁴

Currently, the NICS comprises three distinct sets of FBI files: the Interstate Identification Index (III), the National Crime Information Center (NCIC), and the NICS Index.⁴⁵ To describe these databases, while the III includes individuals' criminal histories in the U.S., NCIC includes information regarding warrants and protection orders. Lastly, the NICS Index "contains criminal and non-criminal records on individuals prohibited from purchasing firearms including previously denied persons, mental defectives/commitments, controlled substance abusers, illegal aliens, dishonorable discharges and citizen renunciates."⁴⁶ These databases of the NICS rely on record submissions, such as criminal records and other records that would disqualify persons from possessing and acquiring firearms from various federal entities, as well as voluntary submissions from individual states.

Furthermore, ever since the establishment of the permanent provisions of the Brady Act in 1998, all states and U.S. territories fall under one of three modes of operation for firearm transfers at FFLs, and these categories are referred to as "full point of contact (full POC), non-POC, and partial-POC."⁴⁷ In particular, with federal law requiring FFLs to initiate a background

⁴³James M. Tien et al., Department of Justice, “Cost-Benefit of Point-of-Contact (POC) Versus Non-POC Firearm Eligibility Background Checks,” (hereinafter “Cost Benefit of Point of Contact”) May 2008, Document No: 222674, 2.

⁴⁴ Ibid.

⁴⁵ Foster, *Federal Firearms Laws: Overview and Selected Legal Issues for the 116th Congress*, 18-19.

⁴⁶ Tien et al., “Cost Benefit of Point of Contact,” ii-iii (2-3).

⁴⁷ Ibid, 3.

check on a purchaser prior to the sale, it gives states the option of serving as a state point of contact, conducting background checks using state and federal records and databases, or having the checks conducted by the FBI. As a result, depending on the State where an FFL is located, it may either be required to contact the FBI or a state point of contact when initiating a background check on a potential firearm buyer. States where FFLs are required to contact a state point of contact are known as full POC states.⁴⁸ Contrary, states where FFLs are required to contact the FBI are known as non-POC states.⁴⁹ Additionally, FFLs in a couple of states are required to contact both the FBI and state point of contact, depending on the type of firearm that is being purchased.⁵⁰ Overall, the method of background checks on firearm purchases from FFLs varies in each State. While some states are either full or partial POC states, most states, including U.S. territories and the District of Columbia, are non-POC states.⁵¹

So, currently, there are thirteen full POC States in the United States that use a point-of-a-contact state agency to conduct background checks for gun transfers from FFLs in their states.⁵² For example, California is one of the thirteen POC States; the California Department of Justice (DOJ), which is a statewide law enforcement agency, is currently serving California's POC for firearm purchaser background checks.⁵³ With this in mind, "Firearm dealers must therefore initiate the background check required by federal law by contacting the California DOJ."⁵⁴ When

⁴⁸ U.S. Federal Bureau of Investigation (FBI), "National Instant Criminal Background Check System (NICS) Federal Firearms Licensee Manual," FBI (FBI, June 4, 2016), <https://www.fbi.gov/file-repository/nics-firearms-licensee-manual-111811.pdf/view>, 4.

⁴⁹ U.S. Federal Bureau of Investigation (FBI), "National Instant Criminal Background Check System (NICS) Federal Firearms Licensee Manual," 4.

⁵⁰ *Ibid.*

⁵¹ U.S. Federal Bureau of Investigation (FBI), "About NICS," (FBI, August 4, 2020), <https://www.fbi.gov/services/cjis/nics/about-nics>.

⁵² FBI, "About Nics."

⁵³ Cal. Penal Code § 28220(b).

⁵⁴ "Background Check Procedures in California." Giffords, February 12, 2021. <https://giffords.org/lawcenter/state-laws/background-check-procedures-in-california/>.

firearm dealers in California submit the necessary information of prospective gun purchasers to the DOJ, the agency is required to check the federal NICS database and its state records, along with those records it is authorized to request from the State Department of State Hospitals.⁵⁵ In the case that the DOJ finds that a purchaser falls under the prohibited group, the DOJ is responsible for notifying the dealer not to deliver the firearm because it would be unlawful.⁵⁶

There are currently 31 non-POC states where NICS provides full service to FFLs. In other words, FFLs in non-POC states are required directly contact the NICS Operations Center via telephone or internet which the FBI controls.⁵⁷ So, in non POC states, when an FFL initiates a NICS check on a buyer, it contacts and submits information regarding the buyer to the FBI, which then checks the NICS to determine whether the purchaser is prohibited under federal law.⁵⁸ On top of that, the FBI currently shares responsibility with six other states known as partial POCs.⁵⁹ Specifically, while FFLs in all six states are required to contact the FBI for long gun background checks, four of these states conduct handgun background checks by using their state agencies, and the other two states "issue handgun permits used for handgun background checks."⁶⁰ Listed in the next page is an up-to-date NICS Participation Map displaying which states and federal territories are full POCs, partial POCs, or non POCs.

⁵⁵ Cal. Penal Code § 28220(a).

⁵⁶ Cal. Penal Code § 28220(c).

⁵⁷ Tien et al., "Cost Benefit of Point of Contact," iii (3).

⁵⁸ U.S. Federal Bureau of Investigation (FBI), "National Instant Criminal Background Check System (NICS) Federal Firearms Licensee Manual," 4.

⁵⁹ FBI, "About NICS."

⁶⁰ Ibid.

NICS Participation Map

37 Non Point-of-Contact (POC) States
Federal Firearms Licensees (FFL) contact FBI for all firearm background checks
13 Full POC States
FFLs contact state for all firearm background checks

4 Partial POC States
FFLs contact state for handguns, and contact FBI for long gun background checks
2 Partial POC States
State-issued handgun permit is used for handguns, and FFLs contact FBI for long gun background checks

*25 Bureau of Alcohol, Tobacco, Firearms and Explosives Qualified Alternate Permits issued by state or local agencies

Please refer to the latest Permanent Brady Permit Chart for specific permit details.
www.atf.gov/rules-and-regulations/permanent-brady-permit-chart

7/2021

Figure 1: NICS Participation Map⁶¹

⁶¹ Ibid.

Additionally, if a transferee possesses certain state firearm permits, a NICS inquiry is not required. In particular, according to the Permanent Brady Permit Chart, federal law under the Brady Act provides an exception to the background checks requirement if “the transferee possesses a State permit that meets certain requirements, including that the State law provides that a NICS check will be conducted before the permit is issued and the permit will not be issued if the person is prohibited from possessing or receiving firearms under Federal, State, or local law.”⁶² These state permits are known as ATF-qualified alternate permits, and currently, twenty-five states have one or more of these permits issued to persons, which can substitute for a NICS background check.⁶³ For example, South Carolina, Texas, Utah, and Wyoming all have a concealed weapons permit that can be acquired by persons and thus, qualify as an alternative to the NICS check required by permanent Brady.⁶⁴

Overall, since the enactment of the permanent provisions of the Brady Act in November of 1998, federal law requires all FFLs throughout the U.S. to initiate a NICS check prior to the transfer of any firearms to unlicensed individuals or individuals without an ATF-qualified alternate permit in order to know if they are prohibited from possessing firearms. The following list of steps describes precisely how these firearm transfers at FFLs take place:

1. Transferee/Purchaser completes and signs Firearm Transactions Record Form (ATF Form 4473). Please refer to the form for additional information.⁶⁵

⁶² U.S. Dept. of Justice. Bureau of Alcohol, Tobacco, Firearms, and Explosives (ATF), “Open Letter to all California Federal Firearms Licensees,” (ATF, October 12, 2004), <https://www.atf.gov/firearms/docs/open-letter/california-oct1998-open-letter-permanent-provisions-brady-law/download>.

⁶³ FBI, “About NICS.”

⁶⁴ U.S. Dept. of Justice. Bureau of Alcohol, Tobacco, Firearms, and Explosives (ATF), “Permanent Brady Permit Chart,” Last Updated June 21, 2020, <https://www.atf.gov/rules-and-regulations/permanent-brady-permit-chart>.

⁶⁵ U.S. Dept. of Justice. Bureau of Alcohol, Tobacco, Firearms, and Explosives (ATF), “Firearms Transaction Record,” Form No.: OMB No. 1140-0020, <https://www.atf.gov/firearms/docs/4473-part-1-firearms-transaction-record-over-counter-atf-form-53009/download>.

- a. Contains relevant information regarding the purchaser, such as name, state of residence, address, race, SSN, date of birth, and government-issued photo identification.
 - b. The transferee answers “yes or no” to questions that ask whether the transferee falls into any prohibited classes, such as having a felony conviction or being adjudicated as a mental defective.
2. FFL verifies the transferee's identity by ensuring the information provided by the transferee matches their government-issued photo ID.⁶⁶
 3. FFL initiates a NICS background check by either contacting the FBI or State POC, depending on the State or U.S. territory:⁶⁷
 - a. Non Point-of-Contact (POC) States: FFL contacts the Federal Bureau of Investigation’s NICS Operations Center (NICS Section) for all firearm transfers, which can be done in several methods. The FBI then conducts the NICS check to determine whether or not the transfer would violate state or federal law.⁶⁸
 - dialing 1-877-FBI- NICS (1-877-324-6427)
 - contact NICS through the internet at www.nicsezcheckfbi.gov.
 - b. Full Point-of-Contact (POC) States: FFL contacts the state POC for all firearm transfers. The state POC then checks whether or not the transfer would violate state or federal law by conducting a NICS check as well as examining its own state databases.⁶⁹
 - Partial Point-of-Contact States: FFL contacts the state POC for handgun transfers and contacts the NICS Operation Center for long gun transfers.⁷⁰
 4. FFL receives a proceed, deny, or delay response.
 - a. A proceed response means that a transferee’s records do not identify them as “being prohibited from possessing or purchasing a firearm.”⁷¹ FFL is permitted to transfer the firearm to the transferee lawfully.
 - b. A denied response means that a transferee's records identify them as “being prohibited from possessing or purchasing a firearm.”⁷² It is unlawful for the FFL to transfer the firearm to the transferee.
 - c. A delayed response means that further examination of the transferee’s records is needed, and if there is no additional response within the waiting period requirements, the firearm transfer may legally proceed afterward to the transferee.

⁶⁶ U.S. Dept. of Justice. Bureau of Alcohol, Tobacco, Firearms, and Explosives (ATF), “Open Letter to all Alabama Federal Firearms Licensees,” (ATF, October 30, 1998), <https://www.atf.gov/firearms/docs/open-letter/alabama-oct1998-open-letter-permanent-provisions-brady-law/download>.

⁶⁷ Frandsen, “Enforcement of the Brady Act,” 3.

⁶⁸ U.S. Federal Bureau of Investigation (FBI), “National Instant Criminal Background Check System (NICS) Federal Firearms Licensee Manual,” 4-5.

⁶⁹ *Ibid.*

⁷⁰ *Ibid.*

⁷¹ Foster, *Federal Firearms Laws: Overview and Selected Legal Issues for the 116th Congress*, 19.

⁷² *Ibid.*

- Federal law (Brady Act) requires all FFLs to wait at least three business days prior to legally transferring any firearm once they have initiated the background check.⁷³
- However, any state can extend this waiting period on FFLs within their State. Subsequently, twenty-one states have adopted distinctive policies that extend the waiting period an FFL must wait after the initiation of a background check.⁷⁴

III. Effectiveness of Federal Law on the Possession and Transfer of Firearms

Since the enactment of the permanent provisions of the Brady Act, several millions of prohibited gun transactions have been prevented. To be specific, approximately "4 million prohibited gun transactions" have been prevented by the Brady Background Check System.⁷⁵ From this understanding, it seems that the GCA's amended provisions on the transfer and possession of firearms have limited and suppressed dangerous persons from acquiring firearms, which would help ensure violent crimes using weapons are lowered.

However, federal restrictions on the transfer and possession of firearms to certain persons have failed to prevent prohibited persons from accessing firearms. This failure stems from a particular set of loopholes and gaps that have undermined these provisions.

A. Unlicensed Gun Sellers

First of all, the most significant loophole that has destabilized regulations on firearm possession is the lack of federal law regulating unlicensed sellers. Since the GCA, federal law has only established regulations on federally licensed gun sellers, which are supposedly the primary sellers who conduct firearm transactions. As previously said, persons engaged in the business of firearms must be federally licensed to either manufacture, import, or sell firearms.

⁷³ Frandsen, "Enforcement of the Brady Act," 4.

⁷⁴ "Close the Charleston Loophole," Everytown Research & Policy, March 4, 2022, <https://everytownresearch.org/solution/close-the-charleston-loophole/>.

⁷⁵ "Brady Background Checks," Brady, accessed May 12, 2022, <https://www.bradyunited.org/our-work/policy/brady-background-checks>.

However, some persons sell firearms in a limited fashion and thus, are not required by federal law to be federally licensed. In other words, "if you only make occasional sales of firearms from your personal collection, you do not need to be licensed."⁷⁶ For example, if a person decided to buy firearms and then resell them through an internet site in order to finance his living and life expenses, resulting to the sale of a few firearms and additional firearms listed for sale, he or she "must be licensed because he is repetitively buying and selling firearms with the primary objective of profit."⁷⁷ On the other hand, if a man inherits a collection of firearms from a family member, who then posts them for sale online and sells these firearms in a series of different transactions in the next year, he is not required to be licensed because he is just liquidating a personal collection and not making additional purchases of firearms to be sold later on.⁷⁸

As a result, there are "two systems of retail gun commerce" in the U.S., "one involving licensed gun retailers and the other based on private-party gun sellers, and only the first of these systems is regulated."⁷⁹ In other words, gun sales made by FFLs are part of the primary market controlled and regulated by the federal government.⁸⁰ The secondary market, "sometimes called the private-party or informal gun market," is not regulated by federal law and consequently allows any person, including prohibited persons, to acquire firearms easily.⁸¹ For instance, a handgun owner without a federal firearm license "may sell, loan, give, or otherwise transfer his handgun to another person without filling out forms, informing any state and federal officials,

⁷⁶ Department of Justice, *Do I Need a License to Buy and Sell Firearms?* 4.

⁷⁷ *Ibid*, 4.

⁷⁸ *Ibid*, 7.

⁷⁹ Glenn Pierce et al, "New Approaches to Understanding and Regulating Primary and Secondary Illegal Firearms," January 2013, document No.: 241021, 10, Department of Justice, <https://www.ojp.gov/pdffiles1/nij/grants/241021.pdf>.

⁸⁰ Glenn Pierce et al, "New Approaches to Understanding and Regulating Primary and Secondary Illegal Firearms,"10.

⁸¹ *Ibid*, 10.

initiating a background check, or abiding by a waiting period.”⁸² Thus, millions of firearms are transferred and sold in the primary and secondary markets.⁸³

More on this, as noted in Section Two of this paper, federal law mandates several restrictions on FFLs, and one of these restrictions is the background check requirement under permanent Brady. However, these restrictions are not levied on unlicensed gun sellers, which means that gun transfers made by an unlicensed seller are not subject to initiating a background check through the NICS directly or a state POC agency. As it is known that background check procedures significantly help to ensure the buyer is not prohibited from possessing a firearm, by not mandating this requirement on all types of firearm transfers whether it’s from a licensed firearm seller or not, this can and has exceptionally destabilized the effectiveness of the Brady Act.⁸⁴

Although federal law does not regulate unlicensed gun sellers who manage the secondary gun market, there are actually 21 states that require criminal background checks for gun sales by unlicensed sellers, with 17 of these states requiring a check on all firearms and four of them only requiring a check on handgun purchases.⁸⁵ In other words, although the federal government has not established any gun law requiring unlicensed gun sellers to complete a background check prior to completing a gun transaction, some states have established laws regulating all firearm sales, including those made by licensed and unlicensed sellers. According to California law, when a purchaser and seller are unlicensed individuals, a licensed dealer must complete the firearm transaction. Notably, in these private sales, the seller is required by California law to

⁸² James B. Jacobs, *Can Gun Control Work?* (New York: Oxford University Press, 2002), 101

⁸³ Jacobs, *Can Gun Control Work?*, 100.

⁸⁴ *Ibid*, 99.

⁸⁵ “Gun Law Navigator: Compare States,” Everytown Gun Law Navigator, accessed May 12, 2022, https://maps.everytownresearch.org/navigator/states.html?dataset=background_checks&states=NY.

deliver the firearm to an FFL, who will then deliver it to the purchaser once he or she passes the background check or there is an expiration of the 10-day waiting period.⁸⁶

However, still, 29 states do not require background checks for gun sales made by unlicensed sellers.⁸⁷ So, neither federal nor state law regulates unlicensed or private sales of firearms in these states, resulting in the completion of many firearm transactions without being subject to certain transfer requirements, such as background checks. As a result, since the secondary gun market is not regulated in these states, prohibited persons, such as criminals with felonies, can easily acquire firearms. Thus, although prohibited persons may be banned from purchasing a firearm from a licensed gun dealer, resulting in thousands of denials, they can still get their hands on a firearm from these secondary gun sources afterward, exemplifying the huge gap in the Brady Law.⁸⁸

To be specific, according to various sources, most firearms acquired by prohibited persons come from the secondary gun market due to its unregulated structure when compared to the primary market of firearms. This seems reasonable when it is known that unlicensed sellers can transfer a firearm without any restrictions, enabling anybody to obtain a gun. Thus, persons who plan to commit crimes intentionally seek to buy firearms from unlicensed sellers, resulting in purchasers who use the secondary gun market being more likely to have a prohibited criminal record than persons trying to purchase firearms from licensed sellers.⁸⁹ “Approximately 1 in every 5 gun sales are conducted without a background check today, due to gun shows, private transactions, and the rise of websites like Armslist.com that facilitate gun sales online,” which

⁸⁶ Cal. Penal Code § 28050(a)-(c).

⁸⁷ “Gun Law Navigator: Compare States,” Everytown Gun Law Navigator”.

⁸⁸ Glenn Pierce et al, “New Approaches to Understanding and Regulating Primary and Secondary Illegal Firearms,” 10.

⁸⁹ “Universal Background Checks.” Giffords, October 4, 2021. <https://giffords.org/lawcenter/gun-laws/policy-areas/background-checks/universal-background-checks/>.

are all part of the secondary market for firearms.⁹⁰ From this opening, about 80% of all firearms acquired for criminal purposes come from unlicensed firearm sellers, and 96% of inmates condemned of crimes involving a firearm “who were already prohibited from possessing a firearm at the time of the offense obtained their firearm from an unlicensed seller.”⁹¹

B. Information Gaps in the NICS

In addition, the information gaps in the NICS system are another concern that has directly impacted the success of the Brady act. Specifically, in comparison between POC states and non-POC states, while POC states use their government agencies to conduct background checks on purchasers from FFLs, relying upon records from NICS and their own state records, the FBI is solely responsible for conducting background checks on firearm purchasers in non-POC states, relying exclusively on the NICS database. Thus, in non-POC states, state databases that hold records on individuals living in those states are not accessible by the FBI; these records can be valuable and crucial because some are not present in the NICS database.⁹² This has resulted in hundreds of thousands of authorized firearm transfers made by the FBI performing background checks in non-POC states, even though these purchasers were considered prohibited individuals in state records. In other words, because the databases of the NICS rely on voluntary record submissions from individual states, the NICS is not a comprehensive system that includes 100% or even a majority of records that could identify an individual as prohibited from acquiring a firearm. This has allowed not all but certainly a large number of prohibited persons to pass

⁹⁰ “Expanding and Strengthening Brady Background Checks (H.R. 8 & S 529),” Brady, accessed May 12, 2022, <https://www.bradyunited.org/legislation/congress-hr8-s529-background-checks>.

⁹¹ Katherine A. Vitte, Jon S. Vernick, and Daniel W. Webster, “Legal Status and Source of Offenders’ Firearms in States with the Least Stringent Criteria for Gun Ownership,” *Injury Prevention* 19, no. 1 (2013): 26-31.

⁹² Foster, *Federal Firearms Laws: Overview and Selected Legal Issues for the 116th Congress*, 19.

background checks and acquire firearms from licensed dealers, especially in non POC states where state records and databases are not accessible.

In particular, the information gaps of the NICS have been a significant problem for non POC states or any states in which FFLs are required to initiate background checks on firearm transferees through the FBI. This is the case because, in states where FFLs directly contact the NICS operation center, the databases of the NICS are the only sources to check for prohibiting records of prospective gun buyers. However, in POC states, because a state agency administrates background checks on firearm transfers rather than the FBI, such as in California, the POC agency does not just use the NICS database. It also has access to state files which are checked to determine whether a purchaser can be transferred a firearm.⁹³ So, in non-POC states, state databases that hold criminal and other prohibiting records on individuals living in those states are not directly accessible to the FBI. The FBI can only access these records if they are submitted into the NICS. As a result, in non POC states, because the databases of NICS are not inclusive, NICS background checks can be inaccurate and thus, result in permitting FFLs to transfer firearms to prohibited individuals.

According to a governmental report, which goes over "an assessment of the cost-benefit of firearm purchase eligibility background checks performed by state point of contacts ... versus those performed by the FBI in non-POC states," it investigates how important state POCs add to the "overall efficacy of firearm eligibility background checks."⁹⁴ The study focuses on three months of data collection made by Georgia and Oregon in 2002. During this time, Georgia and Oregon provided SDC with data on each gun transaction that involved a firearm eligibility check. NICS then performed "follow-up research on every one of the states' POC transactions

⁹³ Tien et al., "Cost Benefit of Point of Contact," iii (3).

⁹⁴ Ibid.

that got a hit on at least one of the three databases of the NICS system.”⁹⁵ The framework of the study concentrates on looking at the "outcomes of firearm eligibility background checks if they are performed by state POCs and then again – in a dual replicative mode – by NICS as they would for non-POC states.”⁹⁶ In other words, this study investigates how NICS checks would perform on transactions already made in the POC states of Georgia and Oregon without any reliance on their state records.⁹⁷

According to the research findings, it was found that NICS checks can be inaccurate since there are some records on individuals that are only available in state records.⁹⁸ While there are several reasons that make it for NICS to have incomplete records on individuals throughout the United States, a majority of these reasons come about due to lacking state contributions to the NICS database. For example, as of 2008, only 42 states contributed to the National Protection Order File, part of NCIC.⁹⁹ Therefore, the research findings discovered that while some transactions were denied by Georgia and Oregon firearm agencies, these duplicate transactions were proceeded by the NICS.¹⁰⁰ Specifically, it was found that POCs can increase deniability by 19.5% compared to non-POC denials.¹⁰¹ These findings mean that NICS checks sometimes authorize gun transactions, allowing some prohibited individuals to acquire firearms lawfully. Therefore, as this research report confirms that state data files add efficacy in ensuring that firearm background checks are correctly executed, it, more importantly, confirms that NICS checks in non-POC states are occasionally misguided due to the incomplete records in NICS.

⁹⁵ Ibid, 18.

⁹⁶ Ibid, v (5).

⁹⁷ Ibid.

⁹⁸ Ibid, iv (4).

⁹⁹ Ibid, v (5).

¹⁰⁰ Ibid, 34-35

¹⁰¹ Ibid, vi (6).

To address the issue of information gaps in the NICS, the National Instant Background Check System Improvement Amendments Act (NIAA) was signed into law in 2008.¹⁰² The gaps in the information available to NICS are even mentioned in the beginning section of the NIAA; "Nearly 21,000,000 criminal records are not accessible by NICS, and millions of criminal records are missing critical data, such as arrest dispositions, due to data backlogs."¹⁰³ According to the act, similar to the statements made in the government report above, the primary causes of error and delay that results in prohibited individuals to occasionally acquire firearms from FFLs is the lack of "updates and available State criminal disposition records and automated access to information concerning persons prohibited from possessing or receiving a firearm because of mental illness, restraining orders, or misdemeanor convictions for domestic violence."¹⁰⁴ So, to improve access to these records, the NIAA imposed "a requirement that federal departments and agencies provide information in records pertaining to prohibited persons on a quarterly basis."¹⁰⁵ It also authorized financial incentives and penalties "tied to submitting records to NICS."¹⁰⁶ Particularly, with respect to NIAA efforts to increase state reporting practices, provisions of the NIAA require states to meet certain goals in providing relevant records that identify individuals prohibited by federal law from possessing firearms to the Attorney General.¹⁰⁷

By expanding state reporting practices of relevant individual records to the NICS through the use of incentives and penalties, it was expected that there would be an increase in records in the NICS. According to the Bureau of Justice, several states have made adjustments and

¹⁰² Pub. L. No. 110–180, 121 Stat. 2559 (2008).

¹⁰³ Ibid.

¹⁰⁴ Ibid.

¹⁰⁵ Foster, *Federal Firearms Laws: Overview and Selected Legal Issues for the 116th Congress*, 20.

¹⁰⁶ Ibid 20.

¹⁰⁷ U.S. Dept. of Justice. Bureau of Justice Statistics, "NICS Act Record Improvement Program," <https://bjs.ojp.gov/programs/nics-improvement-amendments-act#iot06>.

"implemented promising practices for improved record reporting to the National Instant Criminal Background Check System."¹⁰⁸ As a result, in a 2012 report made by the U.S. Government Accountability Office (GAO), it was found that between 2004 to 2011, the total number of mental health records in NICS "increased by approximately 800 percent—from about 126,000 to 1.2 million records" due to an increase in state reporting practices.¹⁰⁹ Likewise, a vast majority of criminal records were also transmitted and made available to NICS.¹¹⁰

However, due to "technological, legal, and other challenges that hinder states' ability to make these records available," the increase in records was mainly derived from the efforts of 12 states.¹¹¹ In particular, it is difficult for states to submit mental health records to NICS because of the lack of statutory authority that explicitly expresses the legality of sharing mental health records.¹¹² In other words, since hospitals and health departments usually hold mental health records, sharing these records is regularly blocked because of privacy concerns. This issue is reported in a variety of reports on NICS reporting; one report made in 2011 found that several obstacles, including privacy concerns, impede state reporting of mental health records in all 50 states.¹¹³ Even after the enactment of the NIAA, an extensive collection of individual records in state and local databases are still not accessed by the NICS.

¹⁰⁸ U.S. Dept. of Justice. Bureau of Justice Statistics, "State Profiles – NARIP," <https://bjs.ojp.gov/programs/nics-improvement-amendments-act/state-profiles#qvik0d>.

¹⁰⁹ U.S. Gov't Accountability Off., GAO-12-684, *Gun Control: Sharing Promising Practices and Assessing Incentives Could Better Position Justice to Assist States in Providing Records for Background Checks* (beginning page not listed).

¹¹⁰ Ibid.

¹¹¹ Ibid.

¹¹² Edward C. Liu et al, *Submission of Mental Health Records to NICS and the HIPAA Privacy Rule*, CRS Report No. R43040, (Washington, DC: Congressional Research Service, 2013), 7, <https://sgp.fas.org/crs/misc/R43040.pdf>.

¹¹³ Ibid, 8.

Overall, with it being established that state agencies usually hold individual records that are sometimes not accessed or held by NICS records, this has had a significant effect on the accuracy of NICS checks, especially in the years prior to the enactment of the NIAA in 2008. During those years, when considering the amount of prohibiting records, such as mental health and criminal records that were not available in NICS, these information gaps have allowed not all but certainly a large number of prohibited persons living in non POC states to pass background checks and acquire firearms from FFLs. One of the most devastating mass shootings occurred because of the incompleteness of the NICS. A Virginia Tech student with a “proven history of mental illness” was able to bypass a NICS check and purchase two firearms from an FFL because NICS did not contain information about his prohibiting mental health history. Thereafter, on April 16, 2007, he used these firearms to kill 32 persons and injure 17 others at the university.¹¹⁴ Moving forth, since 2008, as state reporting practices of prohibiting records increase, so does the number of records in NICS, which helps ensure that persons with prohibiting histories are denied the transfer of firearms from FFLs. However, as data shows in the last decade that some states still lack in submitting certain mental health records to the NICS, it is far from being a comprehensive system, especially as technological, coordination and legal challenges continue to “limit the reporting of mental health records to the NICS.”¹¹⁵

C. Charleston Loophole

As mentioned in Section 2, under federal law, an FFL who has initiated a background check on a transferee can legally sell and transfer the firearm after waiting three business days to be notified whether the sale violates federal or state law.¹¹⁶ In other words, although federal law

¹¹⁴ Pub. L. No. 110–180, 121 Stat. 2559 (2008).

¹¹⁵ Edward C. Liu et al, *Submission of Mental Health Records to NICS and the HIPAA Privacy Rule*, 7.

¹¹⁶ 18 U.S.C. § 922(t)(1).

requires background checks on purchasers from FFLs, gun purchases can still be legally made if a three-day waiting period has passed. In particular, although over 90% of background checks are completed within three business days, some checks require further review. As a result, out of these checks that require further review, which result in delayed NICS transactions, some of them are not completed within three days, allowing dealers to transfer a firearm regardless of the result. When this occurs, it is possible that a prohibited person can retrieve a firearm.

This is especially concerning in states where FFLs are not regulated by any state law that extend the time allowed for completion of a background check. Currently, 21 states have adopted regulations that provide extensions; however, 29 states have not adopted any laws extending the waiting time for gun purchases. So, in these states, FFLs are only subject to waiting three business days after initiation of a background check.¹¹⁷

According to a 2019 NICS Operations Report, over 250,000 transactions handled by the NICS Section in non POC states were not resolved within three business days.¹¹⁸ Of these transactions, over 200,000 remained unresolved, but for the remaining of the transactions, the NICS Section was able to determine whether the final decision was a deny or proceed. Thus, the NICS found that of all background check transaction denials, FFLs transferred firearms to 2,989 prohibited persons due to the inability to complete the background check within three days.¹¹⁹ Similar transfer numbers occurred in prior years, so it is evident that thousands of guns are transferred to prohibited gun owners every year since the enactment of the permanent Brady in 1998.

¹¹⁷ “Background Check Procedures,” Giffords, https://giffords.org/lawcenter/gun-laws/policy-areas/background-checks/background-check-procedures/#footnote_5_5615.

¹¹⁸ U.S. Federal Bureau of Investigation (FBI), “National Instant Criminal Background Check System (NICS) Operations Report,” FBI (FBI, 2019 <https://www.fbi.gov/file-repository/2019-nics-operations-report.pdf/view>), 22.

¹¹⁹ Ibid.

When compared to the other loopholes mentioned in this section, the short waiting provisions that federal law mandates for background checks slightly increase the chances of crimes involving firearms, such as homicides and even mass shootings. Actually, in 2015, nine individuals were killed at a church in Charleston, South Carolina. Although legally prohibited, the shooter could purchase a firearm because a background check was not completed within three days.¹²⁰ Since then, this flaw in the background check system that enables FFLs to transfer a firearm once three business days pass after the initiation of a check has been known as the Charleston Loophole.

The millions of firearm transfers to prohibited persons that the Brady Act prevented do not signify the reduction of crimes involving firearms. Since the passing of Brady's permanent provisions in 1998, federal restrictions on the transfer and possession of firearms in non-POC states, excluding those that have extended federal law with their own state provisions that regulate unlicensed firearm sellers and extended waiting periods, are not effective. In these states, prohibited persons can easily access firearms and thus, commit unlawful acts of gun violence because (1) gun seekers are able to acquire a firearm from an unlicensed seller, such as by purchasing a weapon from a gun show, (2) information gaps in NICS allow some prohibited persons to pass background checks and acquire firearms from FFLs, and (3) NICS checks are not always performed within three business.

IV. Improvements to the Brady Act

Section IV considers what revisions are needed to improve the effectiveness of federal regulations on the possession and transfer of firearms. Based on the findings from Section III,

¹²⁰ “Close the Charleston Loophole,” Everytownresearch, May 13, 2022. <https://everytownresearch.org/solution/close-the-charleston-loophole/>.

which reveal certain loopholes that have undermined Brady's objective of ensuring prohibited persons are barred from acquiring firearms, this report will list a few top ways to ensure this objective is successful. The approaches listed below would be taken in the form of supplementary legislation that expands the current federal framework on transfer restrictions of firearms.

A. Regulating the secondary market of firearms

Through additional legislation, the federal government must require all firearm sellers, including private sellers, to comply with transfer requirements, such as background checks. As previously mentioned, a few states have enacted laws requiring unlicensed sellers to initiate a background check through an FFL prior to transferring firearms unless an exception applies. However, most states in the U.S. do not have any laws that restrict the secondary market of firearms. Amending the Brady act with additional transfer restrictions that would apply to unlicensed gun sellers would eliminate one of the most problematic issues that have undermined the effectiveness of the Brady in preventing dangerous persons from acquiring firearms.

B. Reducing the information gaps of the NICS

A variety of approaches could address the issue of information gaps in the NICS. Congress can continue developing measures similar to the NIAA to further improve the completeness, automation, and transmission of records from federal and state systems. Ever since the NIAA was enacted in 2008, prohibiting records in the NICS, especially mental defective files, have increased exponentially, resulting in hundreds of thousands of records being added to NICS in the 2010s.¹²¹ Thus, Congressional laws that offer grants and penalties to influence state reporting practices are one way to reduce the information gaps of the NICS.

¹²¹ William J. Krouse, *Gun Control Legislation*, 32.

C. Extending the three-day waiting period

To ensure that firearm transfers from FFLs to unlicensed persons cannot be made prior to completing a background check, the federal government must enact a law that extends the current three-day waiting period requirement. As section three mentioned how this short waiting period allows a small percentage of prohibited persons to acquire firearms from FFLs, it is key to extend this waiting period. For background checks that require further review of a transferee's records, an extended waiting period would give enough time for the NICS Section to accurately determine if the transferee has any prohibiting records.

V. A Look at Congress's Recent Firearms Legislation

Section five examines whether Congress has considered any proposals to amend and extend federal provisions on the possession, transfer, or sale of firearms in recent years. According to Congress's recent actions, federal firearms legislation has been a central focus in Congressional discussion, and thus, there have been a variety of congressional proposals on firearms.¹²² In particular, as Congress sought various proposals on firearms regulations in the last few years, some of these proposals have concentrated on amending federal laws concerning the transfer and sale of firearms, such as the Brady Act.¹²³

A. Proposals to Extend Background Checks

To expand firearm background checks, the 117th Congress passed two house bills in March 2021: H.R. 8, the Bipartisan Background Checks Act of 2021 and H.R. 1446, Enhanced Background Checks Act of 2021.¹²⁴

¹²² Foster, *Federal Firearms Laws: Overview and Selected Legal Issues for the 116th Congress*, 35.

¹²³ *Ibid*, 35.

¹²⁴ Bipartisan Background Checks Act of 2021, H.R. 8, 117th Cong. (2021).

If enacted, H.R.8. “prohibits a firearm transfer between private parties unless a licensed gun dealer, manufacturer, or importer first takes possession of the firearm to conduct a background check,” unless an exception applies.¹²⁵ In other words, the bill extends federal background check requirements to also include restricting a majority of private firearm transactions that have been openly unrestricted by federal law. For additional information, refer to the text of the bill.¹²⁶

H.R.1146 would revise “background check requirements applicable to proposed firearm transfers from a federal firearms licensee (e.g., a licensed gun dealer) to an unlicensed person.”¹²⁷ The bill extends the current federal waiting provision adopted from permanent Brady from “3 business days to a minimum of 10 business days.”¹²⁸ So, when an FFL initiates a background check either through the FBI or state POC, before transferring a firearm, FFLs would be required to wait ten days to receive a completed background as well as comply with their state law that may include an even more stringent waiting period.¹²⁹ For additional information, refer to the text of the bill.¹³⁰

B. Provisions to Improve Relevant Records in NICS

In 2018, the Fix NICS Act was passed by Congress, which follows in the same form as the NIAA that was passed in 2008. The Fix NICS Act was enacted to further strengthen the NICS by increasing the record submissions of federal and state agencies.¹³¹ Specifically, federal

¹²⁵ Ibid.

¹²⁶ Ibid.

¹²⁷ Enhanced Background Checks Act of 2021, H.R. 1446, 117th Cong. §2 (2021-2022).

¹²⁸ Ibid.

¹²⁹ Ibid.

¹³⁰ Ibid.

¹³¹ Dept. of Justice, Office of Public Affairs, “Attorney General William P. Barr Releases First-Ever Semiannual Report on the Fix NICS Act,” November 14, 2019, <https://www.justice.gov/opa/pr/attorney-general-william-p-barr-releases-first-ever-semiannual-report-fix-nics-act>

agencies are required to “report certain record submission metrics to the Attorney General in semiannual certifications; and must establish four-year implementation plans to improve records submissions.”¹³² As for state agencies, they are “incentivized with grant preferences to establish four-year implementation plans.”¹³³ As a result, since then, findings have entailed that millions of submitted records entered the three databases of NICS as well as reductions in firearm retrieval referrals.¹³⁴

C. Conclusion to Section V

Overall, as Section Four discussed some of the advances needed to improve background checks on firearm transfers that are aimed at limiting prohibited individuals from acquiring guns, this section examined if Congress has recently considered these approaches through legislation. According to this section, the approaches mentioned in the previous section have been addressed by Congress. However, due to certain factors, some of the Congressional proposals have not yet been fully passed into federal law. Therefore, as of today, the federal objective of preventing prohibited persons because of their risk-related characteristics is still undermined due to certain loopholes and gaps in federal law on the possession and transfer of firearms. Until these gaps are filled in, the United States will continue experiencing crimes involving firearms, such as shootings and other firearm-related offenses.

Final Statements

To reduce gun violence, federal law seeks to prevent certain persons with risk-related characteristics from possessing firearms. Federal concentration for this objective is represented by Congress's supplementary revisions to the Gun Control Act of 1968. Specifically, since the

¹³² Ibid.

¹³³ Ibid.

¹³⁴ Ibid.

enactment of the GCA, which regulates the possession and transfer of firearms accompanied by various other firearms regulations, further congressional legislation, such as the Brady Act, has amended the GCA. The Brady Act introduces a systematic approach that requires a background check for not all but most firearm transfers. As the permanent provisions of Brady were enacted in 1998, its requirement for background checks has and still currently serves as the primary method to prevent certain persons from accessing firearms in the United States. To further evaluate these regulations, especially the requirement of background checks that take a significant part of federal gun reduction efforts, this paper provides an examination and analysis of the federal regulations on the possession and transfer of firearms. As the first section of this paper briefly outlines the federal statutory framework on firearms, the following four sections discuss the development and descriptions of these regulations, their ineffectiveness in limiting gun violence, and possible improvements.